

THE ROLE OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN INCREASING THE POTENTIAL OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES

G‘aybullayev Sarvar O‘ktam o‘g‘li

Teacher of UzMUJF

www.gaybullayevsarvar674@gmail.com

Abstract: The role of marketing, current trends, problems in the network and their solutions are given in this article. The article also discusses the role of textile and knitting enterprises in our country, the creation of an investment environment, the modernization of production and the transformation of the textile and knitting industry into one of the leading sectors of the economy as a result of paying special attention to the production of finished products. will be discussed.

Key words: modernization, knitting, textile, kalava, sewing and knitting, "Luxury plus service", "GSP+", TPMA, "Uztoqimchilik sanoat", modernization and diversification.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan in January-October 2022, a total of 41,764,100 pieces of knitted or woven outerwear were produced by large enterprises, and the growth rate of this production compared to the corresponding period of 2021 was 195.4%. By September, a total of 36,500 tons of knitted or crocheted fabrics were produced by large enterprises, the growth rate of this production and correspondingly compared to the corresponding period of 2021 was 113.8%.

Also, in January-September 2022, the highest share (34.7%) in the production of knitted or crocheted fabrics by large enterprises in the Republic was contributed by the city of Tashkent, 12.7 thousand tons.

In the first two months of 2022, Uzbekistan exported nearly 8,000 tons of knitted goods worth 45.6 million US dollars to 15 foreign countries. Compared to the same period last year, the export volume of knitted goods increased by 8.4 million US dollars.

The countries to which Uzbekistan exported the most knitted products in January-February 2022:

Russia - 14.5 mln

Kyrgyz R. - 14.2 million

Italy - 8.6 million

Ukraine - 2.8 million US dollars

Regions that exported the most knitwear products in two months of 2022:

Tashkent city - 19.1 mln

Tashkent region - 9.1 mln

Andijan region - 6.4 million

Bukhara region - 3 million US dollars

Also, in January-September 2022, the highest share (34.7%) in the production of knitted or crocheted fabrics by large enterprises in the Republic was contributed by the city of Tashkent, 12.7 thousand tons.

At the moment, more than 2,500 enterprises are effectively operating in the network, and these enterprises are engaged in the production of yarn, ready-made gauze and fabrics, sewing-knitting and hosiery products, as well as ready-made products such as carpets.

The high rate of growth of the export volume in the network was ensured by the increase of the physical volume of export of products by 36% and their price by 7.8%. In particular, the increase in the physical volume of the export of ready-made sewing and knitting products was 70.5 percent, in yarn yarn 54 percent, and in hosiery products 53 percent.

Manufactured products were exported to more than 40 countries, such as Russia, China, Turkey, the Republic of Korea, and during the reporting period, the export of products to 2 new foreign markets was mastered.

In particular, yarn produced at the joint enterprise "Indorama Ko'qon textile" in the Fergana region, ready-made knitted products produced at the joint enterprise "Azalia Garment" in the Tashkent region, and men's products produced at the enterprise "Lux plus service" in the Namangan region. Suits and shirts were exported to Kenya.

Sustainable development of the economy, further acceleration of scientific and technical progress, rational use of production potential, comprehensive saving of all types of resources and management of production in accordance with the laws of the market economy are the most important components of the economic strategy of our country. It is impossible to imagine creating a competitive product with high added value without introducing new, modern approaches in the economy. In this regard, we can give an example of the steps taken step by step by the initiatives of our honorable President, and the benefits given to producers and exporters. During the past period, the necessary legal framework and favorable conditions for the development of the textile industry have been formed. Modernization and diversification of the textile industry is the most important condition for increasing the volume and types of ready-made competitive products that are in high demand in foreign markets, increasing the efficiency and profitability of growing and processing raw cotton.

It was reported that Uzbekistan received the status of the beneficiary of the "GSP+" system of special preferences of the European Union. Lucien Devo said that receiving the status of "GSP+" beneficiary provides new opportunities for producers

and exporters of textile products of Uzbekistan. This ensures sustainable growth and diversification of export products.

Along with effective management, attracting new investments, introducing modern techniques and technologies are the most important factors for the development of the textile and clothing industry in Uzbekistan and contribute to increasing its export potential.

As the honorary president of the French textile industry association, he is well acquainted with the activities of French textile companies at the international level, and in this sense, he is interested in developing cooperation with Uzbekistan. He expressed interest in establishing business relations with suppliers who work with European buyers of our country and have the necessary certificates to enter the French market.

At the end of the meeting, an agreement was reached on deepening mutual relations and organizing a presentation of the potential of the textile industry of Uzbekistan for the members of the French Textile Industry Association.

The Agency for Marketing and Advertising of Textile Products (TPMA) has been operating in the market of trade and advertising services since 2007, at the same time it is a constituent unit of the "Uztoqimchilik sanoat" association and represents the interests of local textile enterprises abroad.

TPMA is a modern, fast-growing company specializing in organizing exhibitions and fairs, developing local enterprises in the international arena, developing trade and investment cooperation, developing and expanding cooperation in the field of production and investment, and developing the production and export potential of the domestic enterprise. conclusion of relevant agreements with potential foreign partners.

-TPMA provides businesses with:

- introducing a new enterprise on the market;
- introducing the assortment and types of services to the visitors of the exhibition;
- demonstration of new equipment and facilities;
- positive acceptance of the company's goods;
- increase sales volume;
- establishing new business relationships, finding partners, clients or sponsors;
- conclusion of public contracts;
- Promotion of brand and company image.

TPMA marketing agency is one of the largest and recognized specialists in organizing events not only in our country, but also in the world. Based on it, various international events of local and foreign organizers are regularly held. Its high-tech equipment and the level of professionalism of its staff distinguish the center from the

background of many exhibition sites. For several years, the team has a lot of successful experience in providing consulting services for business, as well as working together with leading experts in the economy and foreign organizations.

Over the years, local enterprises that are part of the "Uztoqimchilik sanoat" association have been participating in international exhibitions held abroad, including Istanbul Dew Bar Lart (Turkey) for light wholesale trade. are active participants. "Istanbul yarn" (Turkey), "Tex World USA" (USA), "quick fabric". The Advertising Agency and the Textile Marketing Agency ensure participation in the preferential fairs in the above events.

In addition, the agency annually organizes events in the Republic of Uzbekistan and abroad, including France, Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, South Korea, Turkey, They are getting tickets to international textile exhibitions and business forum exhibitions held in China, Japan, India, Italy, Vietnam, CIS countries and others.

To achieve the objectives of the textile industry, Export, Textile Sales and Textile Promotion and Promotion Agency is an unrivaled and unique expert in the field of local business promotion and promotion in global markets. .

TPMA agency is always ready to cooperate with all parties interested in the growth of the textile and light industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

List of used literature:

1. Uchkun S., Dilshod N. Process of identifying the significant accounts in the revenue cycle //Journal of marketing, business and management. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 32-36.
2. Dilshod N. Xalqaro standartlar asosida korxonalarda tushumlar auditini tashkil qilish bosqichlari va dastaklarini takomillashtirish //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – C. 105-110.
3. Najmiddinov D. R., Shodlikov D. E. The effect of the secret economy in a daily life of the society //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1A. – C. 56-59.
4. O‘g‘li n. D. R., qizi t. D. Z. Moliya bozorini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo‘nalishlari va unga oid yangi yondashuvlar //Journal of marketing, business and management. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 8. – C. 1-4.
5. G‘Aybullayev Sarvar O. et al. O‘zbekistonda iste‘mol savatchasi hozirgi holatini va uni shakillantirish yo‘nalishlari //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 119-125.
6. G‘aybullayev S. The place of the digital economy today //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 116-126.

7. Gaybulayev Sarvar Uktam ugli, Saitov Sirojiddin, & Davlatboyeva Sojida Oybek qizi. (2022). Small business and private entrepreneurship is a place to provide employment. Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(12), 115–119. Retrieved from <http://ijournal.uz/index.php/jartes/article/view/358> DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429509>

8. Gaybullayev Sarvar, Saitov Sirojiddin, & Pulatova Mashhura Xushnadbek qizi. (2022). Factors affecting labor relations and its wage. Journal of academic research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 1(12), 125–129. Retrieved from <http://ijournal.uz/index.php/jartes/article/view/360> DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7429572>

9. Sarvar O'ktam o'g G. et al. Systematic-situation approach in management //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 999-1008.

